

Expert Evaluation and Review of
**“Estimating Economy-Wide Impact of Research,
Development and Innovation in Egypt”**

Academy of Scientific Research and Technology (ASRT)

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Synopsis:

This professional review for the Academy of Scientific Research and Technology (ASRT) analyzes the technical report of the economy-wide impacts of Research, Development, and Innovation (RDI) in Egypt. The technical report estimates the sectoral and macro-level impacts of Research, Development, and Innovation (RDI) within the Egyptian economy and provides scenario building outcomes towards most likelihood estimates. This is implemented through multi-sector ISIC decomposition and knowledge stock modeling including human capital, education, innovation, labor, and industry-level classifications applied to the simulation scenarios. The report analyzes the alignment of micro-macro RDI metrics to Egypt Vision 2030 targets in order to determine long-run investment returns and critical policy recommendations.

Technical Review- TOC:

- 1) The Scope of RDI (Research, Development and Innovation) in Egypt
- 2) RDI Metrics
- 3) Socio-Economic Impacts
- 4) Multi-sector Decomposition (ISIC Codes)
- 5) Spillover and Supply-Chain Effects
- 6) Public-Private Partnerships and Level 2 Decomposition
- 7) Simulation Model- Structure, Variables, and Scenarios
- 8) Long-Run Investment Returns and Barriers to Entry
- 9) Knowledge Stock Model Specification: Education, Innovation, Industry
- 10) Economy-Wide RDI Impact Factors: Most Likelihood Scenario
- 11) Gap Analysis: Status Quo, Simulation Trends, and Egypt Vision 2030 Targets
- 12) Critical Policy Recommendations
- 13) Conclusion

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